

RUVIFIST: Reconfigurable Underwater Vehicle for Inspection, Free-floating Intervention and Survey Tasks

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Abstract—The development of Autonomous Underwater Reconfigurable Vehicles (AURVs) with the capability of interacting with the surrounding environment and autonomously changing the configuration, according to the task at hand, can represent a real breakthrough in underwater system technologies. Driven by these considerations, an innovative AURV has been developed by the Department of Industrial Engineering of the University of Florence (DIEF), Italy, capable of efficiently reconfiguring its shape according to the task at hand. In particular, the RUVIFIST (Reconfigurable Underwater Vehicle for Inspection, Free-floating Intervention and Survey Tasks) vehicle has been provided with two extreme configurations: a slender (“survey”) configuration for long navigation tasks, and a stocky (“hovering”) configuration designed for challenging goals as intervention operations. Moreover, an accurate description of the overall vehicle is currently provided in this work, starting from the hardware architecture to the developed software framework.

Index Terms—Underwater Robotics, Autonomous Underwater Reconfigurable Vehicles, Marine Robotics

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of vehicles that can incorporate both the Autonomous Underwater Vehicle (AUV) inspection capability and Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROV) intervention functionalities can be considered one of the most challenging tasks of the underwater industry as well as the scientific community. This specific demand can be solved by means of Autonomous Underwater Reconfigurable Vehicles (AURVs), i.e. vehicles which can change their current configuration depending on the demanded task. As far as the Autonomous Underwater Reconfigurable Vehicle (AURV) state of the art is concerned, one of the most innovative vehicles is made by EELUME [1], an Underwater Snake Robot (USR), developed by Subsea Intervention for underwater inspection and manipulation. Another example of AURV was presented by Houston Mechatronics in 2018; the conceptual vehicle, named Aquanaut [2], is a robot with two different configurations: in AUV mode, it can cover long distances while accomplishing tasks like seabed mapping, and inspection of large areas; in ROV mode, the hull can open its structure, exposing two

robotic arms for manipulation operations. Motivated by the previous works, the RUVIFIST (Reconfigurable Underwater Vehicle for Inspection, Free-floating Intervention and Survey Tasks) AURV, capable of efficiently reconfiguring its shape, according to the demanded task, spanning from a “survey”, slender configuration to a “hovering”, stocky layout has been designed by the Department of Industrial Engineering of the University of Florence, Italy. While an exhaustive overview of the AURV modeling is already provided by the authors [3], this work presents an accurate overall description, starting from the hardware architecture to the developed software framework of the first RUVIFIST vehicle prototype.

The paper structure reflects the procedural workflow. In Section II, we summarize the whole hardware architecture of the RUVIFIST vehicle. In particular, the description of each different module has been adequately provided. In Section III, we briefly illustrate the software framework which can manage the transformation capability of the vehicle. Finally, Section IV summarizes the presented research by focusing on the significant accomplished features; moreover, a brief description of the future trends is reviewed.

II. ELECTRO-MECHANICAL DESIGN

With the regard to the AURV architecture, this innovative vehicle has been provided with the capability to actively switch between a “hovering/opened” configuration, with an isotropic behavior functional to face intervention operations, and a “survey/closed” one, with an elongated body that minimizes the hydrodynamic drag in the longitudinal direction and, as a consequence, reducing the power consumption for long mission tasks (see Figure 1 to observe the two different extreme RUVIFIST AURV configurations).

Additionally, the vehicle also changes its thruster configuration in the two extreme shapes. Indeed, by observing the propulsion layouts in the Figure 1, the RUVIFIST AURV has eight different T200 BlueRobotics thrusters: four fixed on the horizontal plane and the other ones aligned in the

Fig. 1. The RUVIFIST AURV in the “hovering/opened” (top) and “survey/closed” (bottom) extreme configurations during a test in a water tank.

vertical direction in the body-fixed frame. Thus, the hovering configuration has a perfect vectored layout in the horizontal plane, with the ability of a fully three-dimensional motion. In the survey configuration the horizontal thrusters result perfectly aligned with the aim of maximizing the thrust in the longitudinal direction. Additionally, each thruster is connected to the main vehicle structure by specific plastic (Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS)) supports obtained with the authors’ laboratory rapid prototyping 3D printer. The transformation ability is available by exploiting six different joints (fixed respectively to the end of a carbon link), two of which are actuated (the ones in the middle of the vehicle) by employing Nema 8 Bipolar stepper motors and the other ones are not actuated. Additionally, the current position of each joint is measured, by using a RLS RM08D high-speed rotary magnetic absolute encoders, in order to check any step loss or prevent a stalling malfunction of the step motors. From a mechanical perspective, the joints have been made in aluminum and also included a worm drive mechanism, with the aim of increasing the produced torque in the opening/closing process (see Figure 2).

To include each different requested functionality, the vehicle has been designed to be provided with several aluminum modules, each with its own specific task. The schematic overview of the RUVIFIST AURV is appropriately presented in Figure

Fig. 2. An image of an actuated joint used in the RUVIFIST vehicle.

Fig. 3. The RUVIFIST AURV schematic overview.

3, which illustrates the four different modules, semantically split into the Core, Antenna and Battery Module, properly described below. More in detail, each module is equipped with its onboard computer (Raspberry PI 4 Model B), capable of managing and analyzing data from onboard sensors, and is physically connected to another by using ethernet cables so that the different computers can be able to communicate with each other. With the regard to the power supply of the overall system, two Battery Modules, placed symmetrically on the vehicle, are responsible for powering the devices in the vehicle. Furthermore, the Antenna Module handles the communication with the ground station by using a Mikrotik Bullet WiFi and a 868+ RFDesign radiomodem. Moreover, the Core Module is provided with an Intel i-7-based main on-board computer to manage the implemented state-of-the-art GNC algorithms, by using the readings from several standard navigation devices such as, for instance, the KVH DSP 1750 single-axis high precision Fiber Optic Gyroscope (FOG), the Teledyne Wayfinder Doppler Velocity Log (DVL), Xsens MTi-300 Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) and U-blox 7P precision Global Positioning System (GPS).

III. SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

The overall RUVIFIST architecture, illustrated in Figure 4, is composed of several blocks, each with a distinct, specific goal. From a practical point of view, each block is composed of one (or more) Robotic Operating System (ROS) interconnected nodes [4].

Fig. 4. The RUVIFIST AURV software framework.

The basic idea behind the overall architecture is that the Configuration Manager node provides the other nodes with the information they need in the current AURV configuration by using the encoder readings. A typical example could be sending the position and orientation of the thrusters to the Actuators node, which is responsible to set the speed demands to the propellers, since the Thrust Allocation Matrix (TAM) changes according to the current configuration. Broadly speaking, the role of the Configuration Manager node is to communicate to other nodes how the system is changing during the transformation. Figure 5 illustrates the several reference frames used with the aim of modeling the AURV transformation kinematics. In particular, we chose the well-known right-handed body reference frame $\{O^b x^b y^b z^b\}$ whose origin is the center of mass of the vehicle, with its x -axis pointing in the forward motion direction, its z -axis pointing down, and its y -axis completing a right-handed reference frame. Furthermore, let be $\{O^B x^B y^B z^B\}$ the base-fixed reference frame, and $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^6$ the joint vector values measured by the encoder readings, the position and orientation of each link (see Figure 5) can be estimated by using a standard forward kinematic methodology (e.g. the Denavit-Hartenberg approach) [5].

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE TRENDS

This work presents the innovative AURV designed by the Department of Industrial Engineering of the University of Florence. As a matter of fact, Autonomous Underwater Reconfigurable Vehicles do arise as a promising tool for incorporating several modules and accomplishing different complex tasks such as intervention, maintenance, and repair operations, in addition to survey missions. Referring to this specific work, each different RUVIFIST module has been accurately described, along with its own particular goal. Furthermore,

Fig. 5. The different reference frames in the RUVIFIST vehicle modeling.

the whole software framework has been hereby presented, starting from the whole GNC devices, to the process which supervises the transformation ability of the vehicle. Future steps will involve testing the proposed methodology over on-field experimental campaigns, from running standard missions to more complex tasks by means of Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms.

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